

CHILEAN SALMON FARMING AND CHINA'S PRESENCE

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Abstract

China has prioritized the expansion of marine resource use as part of its national food security strategy. Increasing environmental constraints within its domestic territory and maritime jurisdiction have led part of this expansion to extend abroad. At the same time, Chile's salmon farming industry has experienced sustained growth, accompanied by rising market concentration and, in 2019, the first major Chinese investment in Chilean salmon production. This case report situates the Joyvio–Australis transaction within the broader evolution of the sector and analyzes the structural characteristics of Chilean salmon farming, along with the implications of this investment. It reviews the environmental impacts associated with the industry and examines how these intersect with significant financial risks, including the ongoing dispute between the former owners of Australis and the new investors. The analysis concludes with reflections on technical approaches and conceptual frameworks for understanding the role of innovation in the sector and assessing the prospects for addressing its current environmental, economic, and governance challenges.

1. Context: Fisheries, Aquaculture, and Food Security in China

China has one of the highest per capita fish consumption rates in the world, averaging approximately 40 kg per year—well above the global mean. However, domestic fishing within its Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ) is insufficient to meet this demand. As a result, China's fisheries policy has increasingly focused on expanding aquaculture and distant-water fishing. This strategy has contributed to China becoming the world's largest producer of fish and mollusks. Its share of global output rose dramatically from 6 percent in 1978 to 40 percent in 2008 (Li et al., 2011: 188). Despite this remarkable expansion, further growth in domestic production faces significant constraints. Environmental

degradation and overfishing have reduced natural capacities, while the sector continues to struggle with biological and chemical water pollution. These environmental pressures are compounded by technological limitations, disease management challenges, and genetic degradation among farmed species (Li et al., 2011).

1.1 Aquaculture in China

China has a millennia-old tradition of aquaculture, particularly in freshwater systems. The sector experienced significant expansion beginning in the 1970s, within the broader context of the country's economic reform policies (Li et al., 2011). A decisive turning point occurred in 1985, when the Chinese government adopted a formal development policy for aquaculture,

fisheries, and fish processing. This policy placed primary emphasis on aquaculture and was later complemented by the promotion of distant-water fishing (Shen and Heino, 2014).

China's aquaculture sector now produces more than 70 million tons of seafood annually. By comparison, the two largest salmon producers, Chile and Norway, each produce approximately 1.5 million tons per year. In China, aquaculture output exceeds total capture fisheries production, making it

the only major producer where aquaculture surpasses wild catch (Li et al., 2011: 187).

Unlike Chile, Norway, and Canada, however, China's aquaculture sector is predominantly freshwater-based and concentrated inland. This branch accounts for most fish production, whereas marine aquaculture in China focuses primarily on mollusks and seaweed (see Figure 1).

Figure 1.

Aquaculture production in China

Source: Li et al (2011: 190).

1.2 Chinese Fisheries

Following the Second World War and the Maoist revolution, China experienced rapid population growth. By the 1950s, fisheries had become a critical source of protein for the population. The sector expanded quickly during that decade and again in the 1970s. However, it was not until the decisive push of economic reforms in the mid-1980s that China emerged as a major actor in global fisheries production.

This growth began to level off toward the end of the twentieth century. Since 1996, overall production has largely stagnated (see Figure 2). China has faced the consequences of exhausting many of its natural capacities, together with the effects of overfishing and the accumulation of pollutants and nutrient loads carried by river systems. These pressures have significantly degraded coastal ecosystems.

Figure 2.
China's Marine Fisheries Output

Source: Shen & Heino (2014: 266).

These constraints affecting both aquaculture and capture fisheries within China's Exclusive Economic Zone have prompted a strategic response: the systematic expansion of distant-water fishing. China's industrial distant-water fleet consists of approximately 2,600 vessels, making it the largest in the world. It is roughly three times larger than the combined fleets of Taiwan, Japan, South

Korea, and Spain. The growth of China's distant-water fishing has broadly paralleled the expansion of its overall fisheries sector. Production increased from approximately 0.1 million tons in 1989 to more than 1.0 million tons in 1997, representing a tenfold rise in just eight years. Since then, output has fluctuated, but the overall trend has been one of stagnation (see Figure 3).

Figure 3.
China's Distant-Water Fishing Fleet

Source: Shen & Heino (2014: 267).

China's expansion into industrial distant-water fishing has generated geopolitical challenges. These tensions are particularly evident in light of its aspiration to assume a more prominent role in global governance without relying on binding agreements, while simultaneously advancing a discourse centered on overcoming established hegemonies (Wirth and Jenne, 2022). In response to accusations that its industrial fleet has engaged in illegal or unregulated fishing, the Xi Jinping administration introduced a foreign policy principle in the maritime domain known as the Maritime Community with a Shared Future. This concept seeks to promote stability and peace in maritime affairs (Song et al., 2022).

In practical terms, current regulatory measures include restrictions on net sizes, seasonal fishing bans, national total catch limits, and controls on fishing capacity through licensing systems and vessel size limitations (Shen and Heino, 2014). Within this broader context, the need to diversify sources of fish supply has become increasingly evident. This provides the backdrop for examining China's involvement in Chilean aquaculture.

2. Methodology

The purpose of this case report is to establish a foundation for the subsequent analysis of China's impacts on Chilean salmon farming.

To this end, it presents an exploratory compilation of information drawn from journalistic, official, corporate, and academic sources. This approach enables a synthesis of the current state of knowledge regarding the sector and China's participation in it, while also identifying specific research questions for the ICLAC nucleus.

In presenting the information, we have assessed its credibility and cross-checked multiple sources. However, it is important to note that the findings have not yet been validated through primary sources, as fieldwork has not been conducted at this stage. This limitation entails the risk that the repetition of inaccurate or imprecise information may create an appearance of reliability. To ensure transparency, journalistic sources are cited in footnotes, allowing for the immediate identification of their institutional origin. All other sources are referenced in accordance with standard academic citation practices.

3. Chilean Salmon Farming

Unlike China, aquaculture development in Chile is a relatively recent phenomenon. To this day it remains unnamed in the "Geografía Económica de Chile" guide published by CORFO in 1962. Although salmon had already been introduced at the beginning of the

twentieth century (Bustos, 2012), the activity had not yet gained economic significance. This section outlines the emergence and rapid expansion of salmon farming in Chile, its principal characteristics, and its spatial organization. It then offers a brief analysis of the key economic actors currently operating in the sector.

3.1 The Emergence of a New Industry

Chilean salmon farming focuses on three species: Atlantic salmon (*Salmo salar*), Pacific salmon (*Oncorhynchus kisutch*, or coho salmon), and rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*). Of these, Atlantic salmon is by far the most significant in terms of production volume (Chávez et al., 2017). All three are introduced species; Atlantic salmon originates from the northern Atlantic Ocean, including the Baltic and Black Seas, while coho salmon and rainbow trout originate from the northern Pacific. None were present in Chile prior to the early twentieth century, when they were introduced for recreational purposes (Bustos, 2012: 222).

Systematic introduction for commercial purposes began only in the 1960s through research initiatives supported by the Japan International Cooperation Agency (JICA) and, beginning in 1978, in collaboration with Fundación Chile and CORFO. These efforts aimed to develop a new export-

oriented sector, building on the climatic and topographic advantages of Chile's southern Pacific coastline for salmon grow-out operations (Hosono, Iizuka, and Katz, 2016).

During the 1980s, the industry gained increasing relevance, and by the mid-1990s it had become Chile's third-largest export sector, after copper and forestry (Barton and Roman, 2016: 653). Despite JICA's prominent role in research and development, direct foreign capital participation remained limited until the early 2000s. High mortality rates, fish escapes, and insufficient infrastructure reduced the sector's attractiveness for large-scale investment (Chávez et al., 2019).

Production of the three species remained relatively balanced until the beginning of the new millennium, when Atlantic salmon farming expanded rapidly. Within the broader policy framework promoting non-traditional exports, cultivation of this species accelerated significantly.

Figure 4.
Annual Harvest of Chilean Salmon Farming (1985–2017)

Source: Chávez et al. (2019: 405).

In 2007, the sector was severely affected by the ISA virus crisis, or infectious salmon anemia, which was first detected in August of that year and spread rapidly thereafter. During 2008 and 2009, it significantly disrupted production at salmon farming sites across Chile (Asche et al., 2009). The outbreak led to a sharp decline in Atlantic salmon output, as this was the only species affected by the

virus. However, the industry recovered within three years, and from 2012 onward Atlantic salmon regained its predominance at even higher levels.

The expansion observed up to 2007 had been driven largely by improvements in industrial organization and production processes. This resulted in a substantial increase in

stocking densities at farming sites, with limited attention to sanitary conditions, weak state oversight, and insufficient ecological knowledge (Bustos, 2012). Following the ISA crisis, the industry was compelled to reorganize its model of “self-regulation,” and production costs rose due to the adoption of stricter sanitary standards. At the same time, certain markets, particularly the United States, expressed growing concern over the intensive use of antibiotics (Chávez et al., 2019).

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A second crisis, known as the “Chilote May” was linked to another major environmental event: the harmful algal bloom, also known as “red tide,” that occurred in the autumn of 2016. The concept of red tide refers to the proliferation of microscopic algae that can lead to the accumulation of toxins in shellfish and fish, prompting temporary bans on harvesting and consumption. Although this phenomenon is natural, the 2016 episode was widely suspected to be linked to salmon farming activities in the region. It was also associated with broader social demands, including calls to reform the Fisheries Law¹ and gave rise to social protests and organized resistance, that were largely carried out and present on social media platforms (Valdebenito Allendes, 2018).

3.2 Spatial Organization in Chile

The production process for farmed salmon consists of three main phases, which are geographically separated.

The freshwater stage. This phase takes place in freshwater environments and replicates the natural early life conditions of wild salmon. It includes incubation, or egg production, followed by the alevin stage and smoltification. Smoltification refers to the stage at which juvenile fish undergo physiological changes that enable them to adapt to saltwater. This transition requires significant biological adjustments and represents a critical production phase, as it is associated with the highest mortality rates in the salmon life cycle. This stage is carried out in specialized facilities located primarily in inland areas of the Los Lagos, Los Ríos, and Araucanía regions. Once completed, the smolts are transported to marine farming centers.

¹ Subsecretaría de Pesca y Acuicultura. (2023). Ley General de Pesca y Acuicultura (Texto Actualizado Incorpora Modificación Ley N° 21.600), tomado de <https://www.subpesca.cl/portal/615/w3-article-88020.html>

Figure 5.
The Three Main Phases of Salmon Production

Source: Montero (2004: 28).

Marine grow-out phase. Marine farming centers are located in the inland sea of Chiloé in the Los Lagos Region and in the fjords of the Aysén and Magallanes regions. These facilities consist mainly of cages installed in cold seawater to replicate natural conditions. Fish are fed in these cages until they reach harvest weight during the grow-out phase. This stage lasts approximately 9 months for Atlantic salmon and rainbow trout, and nearly twice as long for Pacific salmon. In addition to cages and feeding systems, farming centers include the infrastructure necessary for their operation.

Processing. Once harvested, the fish are transported to processing plants, where they are filleted, smoked, or frozen, either as processed products or as whole fish, depending on market demand. According to SERNAPESCA records, there are currently 57 authorized plants in Chile for the slaughter and processing of salmonids. Most are located on the mainland, including Puerto Montt, Calbuco, Talcahuano, Punta Arenas, Porvenir, and Puerto Natales. There are also facilities on the Island of Chiloé, including plants operated by Aquachile in Quellón and Chonchi, and by Cermaq in Dalcahue, Quemchi, and Ancud.

Table 1.
Main Producers of Atlantic Salmon in Chile

Rank	Company	Production (2021, t)	Owners/Origin of Capital
1	AquaChile	128.000	Chilean
2	Multi X	88.000	Mitsui; Cargill & Chilean
3	Cermaq	79.000	Mitsubishi
4	Mowi	66.000	Investment funds (Norway and United States)
5	Australis Seafoods	64.000	Joyvio (China)
6	Salmones Blumar	60.000	Chilean
7	Salmones Camanchaca	36.000	Chilean
8	Salmones Austral	25.000	Chilean
9	Invermar	22.000	Chilean
10	Yadran	21.500	Chilean
	Others	57.000	
	Total	646.500	

Source: Salmonexpert² and Rehner et al 2020.

3.3 Leading Companies in Chilean Salmon Production

In recent years, the sector has undergone significant corporate consolidation, resulting in a market structure in which more than 90 percent of total exports are generated by the ten largest companies. A prominent example of this process is the formation of **AquaChile** through a series of mergers, the most recent taking place in 2019, when AquaChile merged

with Los Fiordos, Salmones Magallanes, and the salmon operations of Friosur (Rehner et al., 2020). This group operates as the salmon-producing arm of Agrosuper, one of Chile’s largest food conglomerates, with the boards of Agrosuper and AquaChile composed of the same individuals³. AquaChile is currently the largest producer in Chilean salmon farming by a wide margin, followed by Multi X and Cermaq (see Table 1).

2 Garcés, J. (2022, July 6). Ranking con productores de salmón Atlántico top: esperan más consolidación. SalmonExpert. From <https://www.salmonexpert.cl/aquachile-chileinvestigacion/ranking-con-productores-de-salmon-atlanticotop-esperan-ms-consolidacin/1297190>

3 Garcés, J. (2022, July 6). Ranking con productores de salmón Atlántico top: esperan más consolidación. SalmonExpert. From <https://www.salmonexpert.cl/aquachile-chileinvestigacion/ranking-con-productores-de-salmon-atlanticotop-esperan-ms-consolidacin/1297190>

Salmones **Multiexport**, which belongs to Multiexport Foods, also known as Multi X⁴) was founded in Puerto Montt in the mid-1980s as a Chilean company. Today, it is majority-owned by foreign capital, with its principal shareholders being Mitsui of Japan and Cargill of the United States, each holding 24.5 percent. Multi X operates three salmon facilities: two in the Los Lagos Region (Puerto Montt) and one in the Magallanes Region (Punta Arenas). Two plants process fresh and frozen products, while one specializes in smoked products.

Cermaq was originally a Norwegian multinational and was later acquired by the Japanese conglomerate Mitsubishi. Most of its farming centers are located in the inland sea of Chiloé, although it also operates in the Aysén and Magallanes regions, including areas north of Riesco Island. The company employs approximately 2,800 workers.

Following these three large firms are three producers of comparable size: **Mowi**, **Australis**, and **Salmones Blumar**. Mowi Chile is part of the Norwegian group Mowi, the world's largest salmon producer. Founded in 1964, the company later went through several name changes, mergers, and acquisitions involving Norwegian and Canadian firms, including Pan Fish, Marine Harvest, Fjord Seafood, Aqua Group, and Northern Harvest.

It eventually reestablished itself under the Mowi brand. In Chile, Mowi employs around 900 people. Its concessions and processing plants previously operated under the Marine Harvest brand.

Australis is a Chilean company that was acquired in 2019 by Joyvio of China. Its case is examined in greater detail in the following section.

Another major Chilean company in the sector is **Salmones Blumar S.A.**, established in 2011 through the merger of the salmon division of Pesquera Itata, founded in 1948, and the company El Golfo. Both were large Chilean companies, with one dedicated to seafood production and the other to the manufacture of fishmeal and fish oil⁵. Blumar's corporate history includes several significant mergers and acquisitions. In 1995, Itata acquired Pesquera Atacama, followed by its merger with Pesquera Confish in 2001. In 2008, Itata purchased 50 percent of St. Andrew, a mussel farming company. Additional joint acquisitions by Itata and El Golfo included the purchase of two-thirds of Pesquera Qurbosa in 2003 and 51 percent of Alimentos Mar Profundo in 2011. Ultimately, after a sustained process of corporate concentration and product diversification, Blumar was formed through the merger of Itata and El Golfo. In 2013, the newly established Blumar, together

4 Founding Partners and Current Board Members: Martín Borda Mingo; José Ramón Gutiérrez Arrivillaga; Carlos Pucci Labatut y Alberto del Pedregal Labbé.

5 See: <https://www.blumar.com/compania>

with Pesquera Bío Bío, began participating in hake fishing and processing.

Pesquera **Camanchaca** is one of the older companies in Chile's seafood and industrial fishing sector. Founded in the 1960s for the production of langoustines, it currently employs approximately 3,700 workers and operates more than 100 salmon and shellfish farming centers. The company also runs three salmon processing plants located in Talcahuano, Tomé, and Calbuco.

In addition to these large firms, several smaller and more specialized companies operate in the sector. **Salmones Austral** emerged in 2013 from the merger of Trusal, Salmones Pacific Star, and Comsur. The first two had long-standing experience in Chilean salmon farming, having been established in the 1980s in the Inland Sea of Chiloé and the Reloncaví Sound. **Invermar** is owned by the Chilean businessman Roberto Izquierdo, who also holds an ownership stake in Diario Financiero. Another Chilean company is **Yadran**, based in Quellón, which specializes in the production of Atlantic salmon.

3.4 Chilean Producers and Their Presence in China

The Chinese consumer market for salmon is relatively new and remains underdeveloped for Chilean producers. As observed with several other consumer goods, direct access

to the Chinese market presents logistical and commercial challenges, including distribution networks and limited market knowledge. In response, Chilean companies have adopted collaborative strategies to strengthen their position. In 2013, the newly formed Blumar, together with Australis, Camanchaca, Yadran, and Marine Farm, established a joint venture to expand their presence in China under the brand "New World Currents."⁶ At its peak, this alliance exported salmon worth USD 100 million to China, representing a significant 10 percent share of that market. However, following Australis's withdrawal after its acquisition by Joyvio in 2019, Camanchaca's exit in 2022, and the broader export crisis triggered by Covid-19, the alliance experienced a sharp decline in sales and was dissolved in 2022⁷. Currently, the Chinese market accounts for only 5 percent of Chilean salmon exports.

3.5 Australis Company

Australis Seafoods, the company examined in this section, belonged until 2019 to a diversified business group owned by Isidoro Quiroga and his family. A brief overview of the group's broader operations is useful

⁶ <https://www.blumar.com/compania>

⁷ Molinari, C. (2022, November 28). Eduardo Goycoolea recounts New World Currents endgame. SeafoodSource. From <https://www.seafoodsource.com/news/supply-trade/chinas-demand-for-chilean-salmon-continues-to-lag-but-expertpredicts-resurgence>

to contextualize the transaction. Quiroga became known for his investments in water rights, energy production, mining, and aquaculture, including activities abroad⁸. In several of these sectors, his business strategy attracted media attention due to highly profitable transactions. One widely reported case involved the sale of consumptive water rights covering significant volumes of water to a Canadian mining company for USD 25.8 million, just one year after those rights had been registered at no cost with the General Water Directorate⁹. In addition, Isidoro Quiroga played a key role in promoting kiwi production in Chile beginning in 1978¹⁰. More recently, he reported investments in Venezuela's financial sector through the acquisition of Trinity's insurance portfolio, and in Colombia, through the purchase of approximately 2,500 hectares for avocado and fruit production under the project Green Super Food.

8 Ex-Ante. (2023, December 17). Isidoro Quiroga, el empresario chileno residente en Londres que está bajo acecho de una multinacional china. From <https://www.ex-ante.cl/isidoro-quiroga-moreno-empresario-acusaciones-joyviosalmones-australis-estafa/>

9 Arellano, A. (2013, December 10). La historia del discreto empresario que se transformó en el zar de las aguas en Chile. CIPER Chile. From <https://www.ciperchile.cl/2013/12/10/la-historia-del-discreto-empresario-que-setransformo-en-el-zar-de-las-aguas-en-chile/>

10 Troncoso Ostornol, J. (2020, May 25). Isidoro Quiroga, el hombre que en menos de un año elevó su patrimonio en más de US\$ 1.500 millones. Diario Financiero. From <https://www.df.cl/empresas/actualidad/isidoro-quiroga-elhombre-que-en-menos-de-un-ano-elevo-su-patrimonio-en>

Regarding salmon farming, Quiroga's involvement is relatively recent. He acquired Australis in 2003, when the company's activities were still concentrated in the freshwater phase of salmon production. Today, Australis operates across all stages of the salmon value chain, beginning with the acquisition of eggs under a long-term supply contract with Aquagen Chile, a company specializing in genetics¹¹. It develops alevin and smolt production through its subsidiary Australis Agua Dulce S.A., formerly Landcatch Chile, with facilities located inland between Curacautín and Villarrica in the Araucanía Region.

Grow-out operations are managed through Australis Mar S.A. in the Aysén Region and through five subsidiary companies in the Magallanes Region, as shown in Figure 7. Australis Mar is also responsible for marketing and exports, primarily to the United States and Japan. In 2013, Australis Seafoods acquired 100 percent of Congelados y Conservas Fitz Roy. Its processing plants are located in the Magallanes Region, specifically in Porvenir (ELDAP), Puerto Natales (Pesquera Álvarez & Álvarez), and Punta Arenas (Chile Seafoods Comercial).

Australis represents a different driving force from most companies in the sector. Unlike firms that emerged from industrial fishing

11 See: www.australis-seafoods.com/australis-seafoods/historia/

Figure 6.
Location of Australis' Alevin and Smolt Production Facilities

Source: Authors' own elaboration based on data from the Environmental Impact Assessment Service

or shellfish farming, its development was primarily linked to an investment opportunity. This trajectory reflects broader structural conditions in Chile. As a small and open economy with growth strongly oriented toward exports, Chile is characterized by relatively high levels of financial liquidity. This

environment has made capital available for investment within an institutional framework favorable to private enterprise, alongside a persistent need to diversify the domestic economy. At the same time, the salmon sector has undergone increasing market concentration. This trend is associated with

Figura 7.
Location of Australis' Alevin and Smolt Production Sites
Australis Companies in the Aysén Region

Australis Companies in the Magallanes Region

Source: Authors' own elaboration based on data from the Environmental Impact Assessment Service

the substantial financial resources required to modernize infrastructure, as well as with the advantages of economies of scale in

production and distribution, particularly when supplying large volumes to key markets such as the United States, Europe, and China.

These dynamics have contributed to a growing financialization of the sector¹². While this phenomenon is observable across multiple industries, in salmon farming it may pose particular challenges due to limited sector-specific expertise and the complexity of relationships with local communities and state authorities.

4. China's Participation in Chilean Salmon Farming

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As of November 2023, there has been only one Chinese investment in the sector: Joyvio's acquisition of Australis. The following section outlines the main characteristics of the Chinese investor and then examines the company's current situation, including the legal disputes in which it is involved.

4.1 Legend Holdings Corporation

Legend is a private Chinese company currently structured as a diversified holding group. It was founded in 1984 as a spin-off created by researchers from the Institute of Computing Technology of the Chinese Academy of Sciences. Initially, the company focused on the development of information

and communication technologies. Liu Chuanzhi, now the principal owner of the Legend group, was among its founding researchers.

Legend subsequently established Lenovo, which became one of the world's largest computer manufacturers after acquiring IBM's personal computer division for USD 1.25 billion in 2004. Legend Holdings Corporation is listed among the world's top 1000 companies, with annual revenues of approximately USD 76 billion¹³. It ranks among China's largest conglomerates¹⁴, employs more than 100,000 people, and manages a diversified portfolio of investments organized into six main business segments:

- **Lenovo:** The Information Technology segment focuses on the development, manufacturing, and sale of electronic and other high-technology products.
- **Banque Internationale:** Provides short-term financing services and customized banking solutions.
- **Financial Investments:** Engages in private equity, venture capital, and other forms of institutional investment.

¹² For a discussion of financialization and its relationship with the local economy, see, for example, Rehner and Rodríguez (2017).

¹³ From Forbes: <https://www.forbes.com/companies/legend-holding/?sh=274f78734914>

¹⁴ Cabello, C. (2018, November 19). El variado portafolio de Joyvio, el gigante chino que comprará Australis. La Tercera. From <https://www.latercera.com/pulso/noticia/variado-portafolio-joyvio-gigante-chino-compraraaustralis/408068/>

- Services: Includes dental and online healthcare services through iBYER Dental, as well as activities in logistics, car leasing, marketing, and other service areas.
- Joyvio: The agriculture and food segment primarily operates in fruit cultivation and sales, as well as tea products.
- Levima: The new materials segment provides services in fine chemicals.

4.2 Joyvio in Chile

Joyvio Group was established in 2012 by Legend Holdings as part of its expansion into the food and beverage sector, an area of strategic relevance and high sensitivity for China and its government due to its direct connection to food security. Within this segment, Joyvio defines itself as an established brand for food and beverage products in China, and as a global food and agribusiness corporation¹⁵

Joyvio is structured around four main business areas: beverages, fruit, animal protein, and packaged foods, each operating through a range of affiliated companies and brands. Before entering the salmon sector, the group had already established a presence in Chile through its fruit division. As a major producer of kiwi and blueberries in China,

Joyvio began expanding into Chile in 2013 by forming an alliance with Subsole, one of the country's leading exporters of grapes, kiwi, cherries, and avocados. In 2022, Subsole was acquired by the U.S.-based company Frutura, and the partnership with Joyvio appears to have concluded. Since 2017, Joy Weng Mau, a subsidiary of Joyvio, has maintained a joint venture with Hortifrut in mainland China to distribute the Chilean company's products in the Chinese market. This collaboration involved a USD 15 million investment by Joy Weng Mau and reportedly included plans to develop berry production in China¹⁶. The subsidiary most directly linked to the salmon sector is Joyvio Food¹⁷, which is part of Joyvio Group and focuses on the processing and commercialization of aquatic products sourced from Alaska, Canada, Greenland, and Argentina.

In 2019, Joyvio Food acquired 100 percent of Australis for USD 921.6 million, marking the highest-value transaction in Chile's aquaculture industry up to that time. The deal reportedly surprised the stock market, as the purchase price exceeded estimated valuations of the recently merged AquaChile,

¹⁵ See: http://www.legendholdings.com.cn/InvestDetail_en/index.aspx?nodeid=1055

¹⁶ See: Reuters (2018, July 9) "Chilena Hortifrut crea sociedad con Joy Wing Mau para distribución en China". From: <https://www.reuters.com/article/alimentos-chile-hortifrutidLTAKBN16R2KO-OUSLB>

¹⁷ Joyvio Food Co. Ltd. was known until 2021 as Joyvio Agriculture Development Co. Ltd., and previously, until 2017, operated under the name Wanfu Biotechnology (Hunan) Agricultural Development Co. Ltd.

even though AquaChile was three times larger than Australis¹⁸. According to the company's first annual report under Joyvio Food's management, Australis achieved a record harvest of 71,976 tons, representing growth of more than 20 percent compared to 2018. The company also consolidated its operations in the Magallanes Region, which accounted for nearly half of total production.

However, Joyvio Food has since faced financial difficulties, reporting significant losses in the first half of 2023. This situation has been accompanied by a substantial decline in its stock market valuation, with its share price losing approximately half of its value since the beginning of 2022¹⁹.

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4.3 Legal Dispute Between Joyvio and Australis

A few years after the sale of Australis by the Chilean group led by Isidoro Quiroga to Joyvio, a serious legal dispute emerged. At the end of 2022, Australis Seafoods self-reported to the Environmental Superintendence for the overproduction of 81,000 tons of salmon between 2018 and 2022. Although the overproduction occurred prior to the sale to the Chinese investor, legal responsibility remains with Australis as a corporate entity, despite the subsequent change in ownership. The excess production affected 33 farming centers across the Magallanes, Aysén, and Los Lagos regions. Compliance with the required corrective measures is estimated to cost Joyvio CLP 63 billion and would entail a temporary suspension of production. From an economic perspective, an even more significant consequence is the need to substantially reduce annual production and sales, which directly diminishes the value of the recently acquired company²⁰.

18 Olivares C., E. (2023, 17 de diciembre). Isidoro Quiroga, el empresario chileno residente en Londres que está bajo acecho de una multinacional china. Ex-Ante. Recuperado de <https://www.ex-ante.cl/isidoro-quiroga-moreno-empresario-acusaciones-joyvio-salmones-australis-estafa/>

19 MarketScreener. (2023). Joyvio Food Co., Ltd. informa los resultados de ganancias para el semestre terminado el 30 de junio de 2023. Recuperado de <https://www.marketscreener.com/quote/stock/JOYVIO-FOOD-CO-LTD-11318071/news/Joyvio-Food-Co-Ltd-Reports-Earnings-Results-for-the-Half-Year-Ended-June-30-2023-44737408/>

20 SalmonExpert. (2023, 14 de julio). Conflicto entre controladores de Australis y el empresario Isidoro Quiroga se amplía. Recuperado de <https://www.salmonexpert.cl/australis-joyvio/conflicto-entre-controladores-de-australis-y-el-empresario-isidoro-quiroga-se-amplia/1544851> y SalmonExpert. (2023, 19 de junio). Australis presenta 21 Programas de Cumplimiento para compensar sobreproducción. Recuperado de <https://www.salmonexpert.cl/australis-seafoods-sobreproduccion/australis-presenta-21-programas-de-cumplimiento-para-compensar-sobreproduccion/1534840>

This situation prompted Joyvio to initiate legal proceedings against the former owners of Australis and senior company executives, alleging that documentation had been manipulated in order to justify a sale price significantly higher than the firm's actual value. As cited by El Mercurio from the legal complaint, the "company was able to present improper revenues and margins that were being generated (and projected to be generated) illegally, thereby allowing it to overvalue the company and obtain payment of an exorbitant price of nearly USD 1 billion"²¹.

In response, the legal representatives of the Quiroga family filed complaints against Joyvio's management, accusing them of defamation in the media. They contend that the underlying cause of the dispute lies in Joyvio's miscalculation in acquiring Australis, which allegedly resulted in a critical financial situation. According to this position, the accusations constitute an attempt to recover part of the investment already made.

In the broader context of scrutiny of Isidoro Quiroga's business activities, media coverage has also referred to his personal relationships with prominent businessmen associated with the Pinochet dictatorship, including

Julio Ponce Lerou and Hernán Büchi²². It is noteworthy that media narratives emphasize this reputational dimension, even though such associations do not necessarily indicate the nature of his business practices.

5. Impacts of Salmon Farming – A Brief Overview

The impacts discussed in this section concern the effects of salmon farming as a whole, rather than those specifically attributable to Joyvio. Where project-specific information has been identified, it is presented as contextual background for more detailed analysis in the following sections.

25

5.1 Economic Effects

"The experience of the Chilean salmon industry is a useful guide to the construction of a model of natural resources-based growth, including innovation and the effects of introducing an innovation in society" (Rabellotti, p. 899, 2017)²³.

21 Molina J., T. (2023, 9 de junio). Caso Australis: Gigante china Joyvio concreta querrela por estafa contra de Isidoro Quiroga y ex ejecutivos de la salmoneira. Emol. Recuperado de <https://www.emol.com/noticias/Economia/2023/06/09/1097671/caso-austalis-querrela-estafa-isidoroquiroga.html>

22 Troncoso Ostornol, J. (2020, 25 de mayo). Isidoro Quiroga, el hombre que en menos de un año elevó su patrimonio en más de US\$ 1.500 millones. Diario Financiero. Recuperado de <https://www.df.cl/empresas/actualidad/isidoro-quiroga-el-hombre-que-en-menos-de-un-ano-elevo-su-patrimonio-en>

23 <https://dfmas.cl/df-mas/coffee-break/isidoro-quiroga-contra-andres-lyon-se-querrela-por-injuria-y-calumnia>

As this quotation suggests, the salmon sector has generated a significant economic impact, particularly at the local level. Beyond innovation itself, its importance lies in the creation of formal employment that has remained relatively stable over time and offers wages above the local average. Initially, the so-called “miracle” of the salmon model in Chiloé was criticized for relying on low-paid labor, weak labor protections, and limited unionization. Over the past two decades, however, the sector has moved toward higher labor standards, increased regulatory oversight, and elevated levels of unionization, including substantial participation by women (Barton and Román, 2016). The industry has also produced notable multiplier effects. Rising demand for infrastructure has stimulated construction activity and supported other regional sectors, such as tourism in Chiloé. In addition, salmon farming has contributed to municipal and regional revenues through licensing fees. Since 2014, specific salmon-related permits have generated revenues distributed equally between regional governments and the municipalities where operational concessions are located (Bustos-Gallardo and Prieto, 2019: 169).

Even prior to its rapid expansion beginning in 2000, salmon farming had been identified as a driver of economic growth in the Los Lagos Region (Barton, 1997). Following the return to democracy and until the ISA crisis, the region experienced positive trends in GDP growth,

poverty reduction, and low unemployment (Bustos and Prieto, 2019). These economic effects also produced deeper social transformations in the islands. Migration toward the Island of Chiloé, as well as from rural areas to urban centers, accelerated, leading to rapid urbanization across the archipelago. Framed within a discourse of modernization and development (Bustos, 2012), this process contributed to cultural and lifestyle changes, reducing the prominence of traditional collective practices (Fløysand and Román, 2008; Barton and Román, 2016: 654).

At the same time, the sector's economic weight has generated increasing regional dependence on salmon farming. This vulnerability became evident during the ISA crisis, which coincided with the global financial crisis, when unemployment rates doubled between 2006 and 2009.

5.2 Environmental Impacts

The environmental impacts of salmon farming arise primarily through three processes: nutrient overloading of marine waters, the intensive use of antibiotics, and the escape of farmed salmon from grow-out cages.

Nutrient overloading occurs during the marine grow-out phase, when large numbers of cages are installed in the fjords of Patagonia and in the Inland Sea of Chiloé. Fish are fed from the surface, and uneaten feed sinks to the seabed along with fish

waste. Given the high stocking densities, the resulting accumulation of organic material can be considerable, promoting the proliferation of certain bacteria. This process can lead to excessive oxygen consumption in the water column, reducing oxygen levels over prolonged periods and damaging the surrounding ecosystem. In severe cases, it may result in hypoxia, defined as oxygen levels below 2 ml/L, or even anoxia, the complete absence of oxygen, conditions under which many species cannot survive.

The intensive use of **antibiotics** in salmon farming has long been recognized not only as an issue of product quality and environmental contamination, but also as a public health concern. The potential genetic transfer of antibiotic resistance poses risks for medical treatment in both humans and animals (Millanao, 2011).

The repeated **escape of farmed salmon** has also been identified as a serious environmental concern, with several incidents involving millions of fish. The ecological consequences include the transmission of disease to other species, the possible establishment of self-sustaining wild populations from escaped individuals, and the displacement of native species through competition for food resources (Sepúlveda et al., 2013). As carnivorous fish, salmon compete with native species such as hake, which is endemic to the southern Pacific waters of Chile. Moreover, because salmonids lack natural predators in

this ecosystem, their competitive advantage over native species is further reinforced. One of the most significant incidents occurred in June 2018, when 800,000 salmon escaped from the Punta Redonda farming center operated by Mowi, formerly Marine Harvest, located approximately 20 km south of Puerto Montt. Critics of salmon farming have noted that incidents of lesser magnitude have led to the suspension of salmon operations elsewhere, including in the U.S. state of Washington on the Pacific coast²⁴.

5.3 Overproduction

Environmental Impact Assessments are mandatory for all salmon farming centers and result in an Environmental Qualification Resolution that establishes the maximum authorized biomass production for each site. In recent years, several cases of overproduction have been reported, including voluntary self-reports. For example, in May 2023, Mowi acknowledged exceeding the authorized limit by 13 percent at one of its farming centers. The company argued that when production across its 53 centers between 2019 and 2022 is aggregated, total harvest reached only 78 percent of the authorized volume of 317,000

²⁴ El Mostrador. (2018, 9 de julio). Greenpeace y escape de más de 800.000 salmónes con antibióticos: "Fugas mucho menores han sellado la suerte de la industria en otros países". Recuperado de <https://www.elmostrador.cl/agenda-pais/2018/07/09/greenpeace-y-escape-de-mas-de-800-000-salmones-con-antibioticos-fugas-mucho-menores-han-sellado-la-suerte-de-la-industria-en-otros-paises/>

tons²⁵. This position highlights a question regarding scale and location, since most irregularities occur in fjord areas. Treating excess production at one site as balanced by lower output elsewhere—such as in the Inland Sea of Chiloé—overlooks the localized nature of environmental impacts. Australis has also reported overproduction totaling 85,000 tons between 2014 and 2022. Given that the company's average annual production is approximately 18,000 tons, this constitutes a significant breach of its authorized limits.

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Nova Austral, a Norwegian company, has been accused of exceeding authorized production for two consecutive years at its “Canal Cockburn 13” site, located within Alberto de Agostini National Park, by 850 and 2,460 tons respectively. These figures correspond to 16 percent and 46 percent above the permitted levels²⁶. The same source reports that Salmones Blumar Magallanes exceeded its authorized quota by 3,447 tons, or 69 percent, at the Mina Elena farming center north of Riesco Island.

In terms of enforcement over the past decade, Australis stands out for having received a

high number of sanctions, largely as a result of its self-reports, as shown in Figure 8. AquaChile has received eight sanctions and Mowi four. This is particularly notable given that Los Fiordos is part of AquaChile and that Marine Harvest later became Mowi.

Public debates on foreign direct investment often include the claim that companies seek out countries with weaker environmental regulations in order to establish polluting operations. However, empirical evidence supporting this argument is limited. The pattern of sanctions observed in the Chilean case does not provide clear confirmation of such a dynamic. Nonetheless, in the context of global aquaculture, Abate et al. (2016) identify stronger growth trends in countries with less stringent environmental regulation and oversight.

25 Equipo DF MAS. (2023, 1 de junio). Sobreproducción de salmones: SMA formula cargos a noruega Mowi. Diario Financiero. Recuperado de <https://dfmas.df.cl/df-mas/coffee-break/no-solo-australis-sma-sanciona-a-mowi-por-sobreproduccion-de-salmones>

26 Aparicio, E. (2023, 7 de junio). Otra vez: SMA formula cargos por sobreproducción a salmoneas en la Patagonia. El Mostrador. Recuperado de <https://www.elmostrador.cl/cultura/2023/06/07/otra-vez-sma-formula-cargos-por-sobreproduccion-a-salmoneras/>

Figure 8.
Companies Sanctioned for Overproduction (2013–2022)

Source: El Mostrador.²⁷

5.4 Territorial Conflicts

It is notable that the highest number of sanctions has been recorded in the southernmost regions, particularly in Magallanes, where salmon farming operations overlap with protected areas. This reality challenges the industry’s narrative that it operates under high environmental standards in “pristine” waters. For example, Nova Austral, which operates exclusively in the Magallanes Region, main-

tains that natural conditions allow it to farm without antibiotics or fertilizers. However, some of its operations are located within national park territories, and the company has received multiple sanctions for overproduction.

Salmon farming also generates tensions with small- and medium-scale fisheries due to both its environmental impacts and the extensive infrastructure it requires. By contrast, mid-sized fishing operations generally have a less intensive ecological footprint. Conflicts with traditional territorial uses—including artisanal fishing and the extraction of benthic resources—are therefore evident. Territorial disputes involving salmon farms have a clear environmental dimension, as their impacts

²⁷ Cossio López, H. (2023, 14 de abril). Al menos 16 centros de salmónes no dieron respiro a las aguas de la Patagonia al sobreproducir en ciclos consecutivos. El Mostrador. Recuperado de <https://www.elmostrador.cl/noticias/pais/2023/04/14/al-menos-16-centros-de-salmones-no-dieron-respiro-a-las-aguas-de-la-patagonia-al-sobreproducir-en-ciclos-consecutivos/>

Figura 9.

Ranking of Companies with Concessions Granted within Protected Natural Areas

Source: Mongabay²⁸ based on data from the Subsecretariat for Fisheries.

directly affect other local activities. These include the contamination of waters within protected areas and negative effects on ma-

rine species through competition or pollution, particularly where salmon farming overlaps with local fisheries.²⁹

28 Carrere, M., & Romo, V. (2021, March 17). Chile: 416 concesiones para salmonicultura están en áreas protegidas. Mongabay. From <https://es.mongabay.com/2021/03/chile-416-concesiones-para-salmonicultura-estan-en-areas-protegidas/>

29 Chile. Biblioteca del Congreso Nacional. (2021). Ley N° 21.600 que crea el Servicio de Biodiversidad y Áreas Protegidas y el Sistema Nacional de Áreas Protegidas. From <https://www.bcn.cl/leychile/navegar?idNorma=1195666>

These tensions are further compounded by a cultural and ideological conflict between communal uses of nature and the commodification of natural resources promoted by salmon aquaculture. This commodification extends beyond private ownership of the fish themselves, whether as eggs, alevins, smolts, or adults, to encompass the productive use of water. In this way, it acquires a distinct territorial dimension and intersects with more traditional forms of water use (Bustos-Gallardo and Prieto, 2019).

This broader tension is reflected in the position of Indigenous communities. As stated in a public letter by Kawésqar communities, “The dispossession of the sea from the Kawésqar eliminates the material basis of identity, worldview, and ancestral fishing, hunting, and gathering activities of this nomadic canoeing people who have inhabited the western Patagonian archipelago for 6,000 years” (Contreras and Dauré, 2020: 163). In response, Kawésqar communities have submitted requests to establish a Marine and Coastal Protected Area of Multiple Uses (Contreras and Dauré, 2020: 162). These concerns are also reflected in the recent creation of Kawésqar National Park and a marine protected area adjacent to Alberto de Agostini National Park (Contreras and Dauré, 2020: 162).

In this context, it is particularly significant that the expansion of farming centers into the Magallanes Region, including operations

within protected areas, has been led primarily by the largest companies with the greatest financial capacity, as shown in Figure 9. Australis ranks second in terms of the number of operations located within protected areas.

The recent debate surrounding the creation of the National Protected Areas Service under Law 21.600³⁰ was especially contentious in relation to salmon farming, as existing concessions overlap geographically with national parks. Although salmon aquaculture is not a traditional or ancestral activity, companies have sought to preserve the continuity of their concessions. This has intensified discussions not only about the trade-off between employment and income generation on the one hand and environmental costs on the other, but also about the concept of introduced species and its use as a basis for legitimizing such activities within protected areas.

30 Chile. Biblioteca del Congreso Nacional. (2021). Ley N° 21.600 que crea el Servicio de Biodiversidad y Áreas Protegidas y el Sistema Nacional de Áreas Protegidas. From [https:// www.bcn.cl/leychile/navegar?idNorma=1195666](https://www.bcn.cl/leychile/navegar?idNorma=1195666)

6. Looking Ahead: Innovation and the Pursuit of Sustainability

As global awareness of food security and climate change has intensified, narratives emphasizing the potential of aquaculture to address these challenges have gained prominence. At the same time, criticisms of current practices, particularly in salmon farming, have become increasingly visible. In response, a range of options has been identified to address these concerns (Christiansen and Jakobsen, 2017: 159), including technical approaches such as:

- “Smart” biological approaches, including the use of diverse species
- Reducing stocking densities at farming sites and utilizing stronger currents to enhance fish immunity
- Extending the smoltification phase on land
- Employing closed containment systems in seawater
- Developing organic salmon, particularly in relation to feed and medication practices
- Expanding offshore salmon farming
- Promoting land-based salmon farming

Many of these initiatives are currently being developed in Norway, where innovation

in salmon farming is more advanced and actively supported by the public sector as a strategy to mitigate environmental risks. For example, technical measures have been introduced to reduce the spread of sea lice—a major sanitary threat to farming centers that also serves as a vector for other diseases (Sjøtun et al., 2022).

Innovation in aquaculture, however, extends beyond technical and scientific responses to environmental challenges. In Norway, it has also contributed to the development of local production clusters and innovation hubs (Sjøtun and Njøs, 2019). Bergesen and Tveterås (2019) document the intensive and expanding innovation activity within Norway’s aquaculture and fisheries sectors, arguing that it has supported the formation of a national innovation system. They emphasize the active involvement of firms in generating specialized knowledge, increasing value added, improving labor productivity, and introducing numerous process innovations, often in close collaboration with local suppliers.

In Chile, the emergence of salmon farming represented the introduction of a new production model and product through foreign agencies, particularly JICA, in cooperation with local actors such as CORFO. Although Chile has become one of the world’s leading salmon producers, it is not widely regarded as a leader in sectoral innovation. This is noteworthy given that the

Chilean state provides targeted programs and research funding to the industry, an approach that some critics describe as reflecting a productivist orientation in scientific policy (Barton, Román, and Rehner, 2019). Private actors also promote innovation, including the Technological Institute of Salmon (INTESAL), which is affiliated with the industry association SalmonChile.

Several dynamics converge in this context: (1) global environmental challenges; (2) local environmental and social impacts; (3) the availability of technical and organizational responses to mitigate these impacts (Sjøtun et al., 2022); and (4) the emergence of new risks generated by the technologies employed. Together, these factors create an opportunity to evaluate proposed solutions from a sustainability perspective and underscore the urgency of such analysis (O’Ryan and Pereira, 2015; Olesen, Myhr, and Rosendal, 2010).

Within this broader debate, the concept of Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) has emerged as particularly promising. It is being explored both conceptually and in practical application to salmon farming (Barton, Román, and Rehner, 2019; Uyarra, Ribeiro, and Dale-Clough, 2019). In this framework, local knowledge and transdisciplinary approaches offer the potential to address existing gaps in scientific understanding while advancing community rights within what has been

described as “Marine Democracy” (Anbleyth-Evans, 2022).

7. Conclusions

Chilean salmon farming is a sector of major economic importance for the southern regions of the country and holds significant weight at the global level. Over the past decades, it has undergone substantial corporate concentration through mergers and acquisitions, resulting in the predominance of six large companies, alongside several smaller firms of Chilean ownership. At the same time, China faces considerable environmental pressures within its own territory and maritime zone. In this context, food security has become an increasingly central policy priority, and in the case of marine products, outward expansion through foreign direct investment has emerged as a strategic response.

Through the acquisition of Australis, a major actor in Chilean salmon farming, Joyvio gained access to an alternative source of marine protein for China and the opportunity to establish a long-term presence in the sector. This objective was likely embedded in its broader strategic planning. However, along with Australis’s productive assets, Joyvio also assumed significant environmental liabilities, reputational exposure, and financial risks. These risks may be linked, at least in part,

to decisions influenced more by financial considerations than by deep sector-specific expertise. Joyvio is not responsible for the years of overproduction that preceded its acquisition, nor for earlier decisions to locate farming centers within or near protected natural areas. Nevertheless, it is now among the companies most directly exposed to environmental and territorial conflicts. It would be unrealistic to expect a relatively new entrant, both to the salmon sector and to the Chilean regulatory and territorial context, to rapidly design and implement comprehensive technical solutions and a robust sustainability agenda. At the same time, as part of Legend Holdings, a conglomerate that has previously demonstrated the capacity to combine innovation with financial expansion, the trajectory of this investment remains uncertain. Whether innovation or financialization will ultimately shape its long-term approach remains an open question.

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